

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Markaziy Osiyo mamalakatlarida sanoat rivojlanishining qiyosiy tahlili

Baqoyev Husan Nuriddinovich

Navoiy innovatsiyalar universiteti, Navoiy shahri, O'zbekiston

Annotatsiya:

Maqolada O'zbekiston, Qozog'iston va Qirg'izistonda 2015–2024-yillar davomida sanoat tarmog'ining rivojlanish tendensiyalari solishtirma statistik tahlil asosida o'rganilgan. Sanoat mahsuloti hajmi, sanoatda bandlik va mehnat unumdorligi ko'rsatkichlari tahlil qilingan. Valyuta kurslarining ta'siri hamda sanoat samaradorligidagi farqlar aniqlangan. Olingan natijalar sanoat siyosatini takomillashtirish bo'yicha ilmiy-amaliy xulosalar chiqarish imkonini beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: sanoat rivoji, sanoat mahsuloti, mehnat unumdorligi, bandlik, statistik tahlil, solishtirma tahlil, prognoz, Markaziy Osiyo.

So'nggi yillarda Markaziy Osiyo mamlakatlarida sanoat tarmog'ining rivojlanishi milliy iqtisodiy siyosatning ustuvor yo'nalishlaridan biri sifatida qaralmoqda. Xususan, O'zbekiston, Qozog'iston va Qirg'iziston respublikalarida sanoat ishlab chiqarishini kengaytirish, uning tarkibiy tuzilmasini diversifikatsiya qilish hamda sanoatda mehnat unumdorligini oshirishga qaratilgan tizimli islohotlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Ushbu jarayonlar sanoat tarmog'ining iqtisodiy o'sish, bandlikni ta'minlash va eksport salohiyatini oshirishdagi rolini yanada kuchaytirmoqda. Mazkur maqolaning asosiy maqsadi O'zbekiston, Qozog'iston va Qirg'iziston respublikalarida 2015–2024-yillar davomida sanoat tarmog'ining rivojlanish tendensiyalarini solishtirma statistik tahlil asosida baholashdan iborat. Tadqiqot doirasida sanoat mahsuloti hajmining dinamikasi, o'sish sur'atlari, sanoatda bandlik ko'rsatkichlari hamda mehnat unumdorligi darajasi tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, sanoat mahsuloti hajmining bandlar soniga nisbatan o'sish sur'atlari va ularning prognoz ko'rsatkichlari orqali sanoat rivojlanishining istiqbollari aniqlanadi [1]. Ushbu solishtirma statistik tahlil natijasida mamlakatlar o'rtasidagi sanoat rivojlanishidagi farqlar, ustun va zaif jihatlar aniqlanib, sanoat tarmog'ini rivojlantirish bo'yicha ilmiy-amaliy xulosalar chiqarish imkoniyati yaratiladi [2]. Olingan natijalar sanoat siyosatini takomillashtirish, mehnat unumdorligini oshirish va sanoatning iqtisodiy o'sishdagi rolini kuchaytirishga qaratilgan qarorlarni ilmiy asoslashda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi [3].

1-jadval ma'lumotlari O'zbekiston, Qozog'iston va Qirg'izistonda 2015–2024- yillar davomida sanoat mahsuloti hajmining barqaror o'sish tendensiyasini ko'rsatadi.

Manba: www.stat.uz, www.stat.gov.kz, <https://taldau.stat.gov.kz/ru/> www.stat.gov.kg saytlari ma'lumotlari asosida muallif tomonidan tuzilgan. [4], [5], [6]

Tahlil natijalariga ko'ra, milliy valyutada ifodalangan sanoat mahsuloti hajmi eng yuqori o'sish sur'ati O'zbekistonda kuzatilgan bo'lib, 2024-yilda 2015-yilga nisbatan qariyb 9 barobar oshgan. Qozog'iston va Qirg'izistonda ham sanoat mahsuloti hajmi ijobiy dinamikaga ega bo'lsa-da, o'sish sur'atlari O'zbekistonga nisbatan pastroq bo'lgan.

1-jadval. O'zbekiston, Qozog'iston va Qirg'izistonda 2015–2024-yillarda sanoat mahsuloti hajmi va sanoatda bandlar soni dinamikasi

Yillar	Sanoat ishlab chiqarish hajmi			Sanoatda bandlar soni		
	O'zbekiston (mlrd so'm)	Qozog'iston (mlrd tenge)	Qirg'iziston (mln som)	O'zbekiston (ming kishi)	Qozog'iston (ming kishi)	Qirg'iziston (ming kishi)
2015	97 598,2	14 931,4	181 026,7	1768,7	1083,7	226,2
2016	111 869,4	19 026,8	209 812,0	1802,4	1087,2	238,7
2017	148 816,0	22 790,2	237 225,3	1826,8	1090,4	288,4
2018	235 340,7	27 218,1	257 348,5	1802,9	1097,8	344,0
2019	322 535,8	29 380,3	283 971,7	1821,5	1094,9	363,6
2020	368 740,2	27 028,5	325 090,1	1809,5	1089,2	344,0
2021	456 056,1	37 606,2	370 533,8	1863,2	1098,0	363,2
2022	553 265,0	48 777,1	435 815,6	1810,6	1121,2	360,0
2023	658 991,7	46 991,8	495 344,0	1835,9	1121,5	356,3
2024	880 198,5	51 469,1	585 275,8	1729,3	1157,8	375,7
O'zgarish 2024/2015	9,02	3,45	3,23	0,98	1,07	1,66
O'zgarish 2024/2019	2,73	1,75	2,06	0,95	1,06	1,03

AQSh dollaridagi ifodada esa valyuta kurslari ta'siri tufayli ayrim yillarda o'sish sur'atlarining tebranishi kuzatiladi. Umuman olganda, sanoat tarmog'i barcha uch mamlakat iqtisodiyotida yetakchi o'sish manbalaridan biri bo'lib qolmoqda.

Ayniqsa, O'zbekistonda 2017-yilgacha amal qilgan qat'iy valyuta tartibi va 2017-yildan keyingi valyuta liberallashuvi sanoat ko'rsatkichlarining AQSh dollaridagi ifodasiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatgan. Liberallashuvdan keyingi davrda so'm kursining bozor mexanizmlariga moslashuvi natijasida sanoat mahsuloti hajmining dollar ekvivalentida yanada realroq baholanishiga erishilgan. Bu holat sanoat rivojlanishini xalqaro miqyosda taqqoslash imkoniyatlarini kengaytirgan.

2-jadval. O'zbekiston, Qozog'iston va Qirg'izistonda 2015-2024-yillardagi sanoat mahsuloti hajmining o'sish sur'ati

Yillar	Mln. AQSh dollarida			O'zbekiston sanoat mahsuloti hajmining nisbati	
	O'zbekistonda	Qozog'istonda	Qirg'izistonda	Qozog'istonga nisbatan	Qirg'izistonga nisbatan
2015	38 005,3	67 258,6	2 878,0	0,57	13,21
2016	37 726,2	55 797,1	3 001,6	0,68	12,57
2017	29 100,3	69 908,6	3 448,0	0,42	8,44
2018	29 163,9	78 893,0	3 762,4	0,37	7,75
2019	36 502,5	76 911,8	4 068,4	0,47	8,97
2020	36 669,4	65 603,2	4 288,8	0,56	8,55
2021	42 983,6	88 485,2	4 400,6	0,49	9,77
2022	50 063,8	106 037,2	5 276,2	0,47	9,49
2023	56 152,3	104 426,2	5 693,6	0,54	9,86
2024	69 566,1	108 356,0	6 576,1	0,64	10,58
O'zgarish 2024/2015	1,83	1,61	2,28	1,14	0,80
O'zgarish 2024/2019	1,91	1,41	1,62	1,35	1,18

Manba: www.stat.uz, www.stat.gov.kz, <https://taldau.stat.gov.kz/ru/>
www.stat.gov.kg saytlari ma'lumotlari asosida muallif ishlanmasi. [4], [5], [6]

2-jadvalda sanoat mahsuloti hajmining AQSh dollaridagi qiymatlari mamlakatlar kesimida sezilarli farqlanishi kuzatiladi. O'zbekistonda 2015–2016- yillarda o'sish sur'atlarining past yoki manfiy bo'lishi asosan valyuta kursining ma'muriy tartibga solinishi bilan izohlanadi; bu holat dollar ekvivalentida ishlab chiqarish natijalarini real aks ettirishni cheklagan. 2017-yildan keyin valyuta liberallashuvi, investitsiya muhiti

yaxshilanishi va sanoatni kengaytirishga qaratilgan davlat dasturlari hisobiga o'sish sur'atlari barqarorlashib, tezlashgan. Natijada, O'zbekistonning sanoat o'sishi dollar ifodasida ham izchil ijobiy trayektoriyaga o'tdi.

Qozog'istonda o'sish sur'atlari nisbatan yuqori tebranishlarga ega bo'lib, ayrim yillarda keskin pasayishlar qayd etiladi. Buning asosiy sababi — sanoat tuzilmasining xomashyo sektoriga yuqori darajada bog'liqligi va jahon bozorlaridagi narx kon'yunkturasining ta'siri. Shuning uchun, Qozog'istonda o'sish sur'atlari ayrim yillarda O'zbekistondan yuqori bo'lsa-da, barqarorlik darajasi pastroq bo'lib qolmoqda.

Qirg'izistonda sanoat o'sish sur'atlari ko'pincha ijobiy, ammo past va o'zgaruvchan xarakterga ega. Bunga sanoat bazasining cheklanganligi, ishlab chiqarish hajmlarining kichikligi va ayrim yirik loyihalarga qaramlik sabab bo'lmoqda. Natijada, dollar ifodasidagi o'sish sur'atlari mavjud bo'lsa-da, ularning iqtisodiyotga umumiy ta'siri nisbatan cheklangan.

2-jadvalning 5- va 6-ustunlarida O'zbekistonda sanoat mahsuloti hajmining AQSh dollaridagi qiymati Qozog'iston va Qirg'iziston ko'rsatkichlariga nisbatan ifodalangan.

3-jadvalda sanoatda bandlar soni hamda bir bandga to'g'ri keladigan sanoat mahsuloti hajmi ko'rsatkichlari orqali sanoat rivojlanishining miqdoriy emas, balki sifat jihatlari tahlil qilinadi. Ushbu yondashuv sanoat o'sishining faqat bandlar soni hisobiga emas, balki mehnat unumdorligi orqali ta'minlanayotganini aniqlash imkonini beradi.

Tahlil natijalari O'zbekistonda sanoat mahsuloti hajmi bandlar soniga nisbatan tezroq oshib borayotganini ko'rsatadi, bu esa sanoatda samaradorlikning ortib borayotganidan dalolat beradi. Qozog'istonda bir bandga to'g'ri keladigan sanoat mahsuloti yuqori bo'lsa-da, uning o'sish sur'ati nisbatan barqaror emas. Qirg'izistonda esa bandlar soni va mahsulot hajmi o'rtasidagi nomutanosiblik sanoat samaradorligining pastligidan dalolat beradi. Umuman olganda, mazkur tahlil sanoat rivojlanishining ekstensiv yoki intensiv xarakterga ega ekanini aniqlashga xizmat qiladi. Olingan natijalar sanoat siyosatini takomillashtirishda mehnat unumdorligini oshirishga qaratilgan choralar muhimligini asoslab beradi.

3-jadval. O'zbekiston, Qozog'iston va Qirg'izistonda 2015–2024-yillarda sanoatda bandlar soni hamda sanoatda bandlarga mos sanoat mahsuloti hajmi va nisbati

Yillar	Sanoatda bandlar soni (ming kishi)			Sanoat mahsuloti hajmi (1000 \$)			O'zbekistonda sanoatda bandlarga mos mahsulot	
	O'zbekistonda	Qozog'istonda	Qirg'izistonda	O'zbekistonda	Qozog'istonda	Qirg'izistonda	Qozog'istonga nisbatan	Qirg'izistonga nisbatan
2015	1768,7	1083,7	226,2	21,488	62,064	12,723	0,35	1,69
2016	1802,4	1087,2	238,7	20,931	51,322	12,575	0,41	1,66
2017	1826,8	1090,4	288,4	15,930	64,113	11,956	0,25	1,33
2018	1802,9	1097,8	344,0	16,176	71,865	10,937	0,23	1,48
2019	1821,5	1094,9	363,6	20,040	70,246	11,189	0,29	1,79
2020	1809,5	1089,2	344,0	20,265	60,231	12,467	0,34	1,63
2021	1863,2	1098,0	363,2	23,070	80,588	12,116	0,29	1,90
2022	1810,6	1121,2	360,0	27,650	94,575	14,656	0,29	1,89
2023	1835,9	1121,5	356,3	30,586	93,113	15,980	0,33	1,91
2024	1729,3	1157,8	375,7	40,228	93,588	17,504	0,43	2,30
O'zgarish 2024/2015	0,98	1,07	1,66	1,87	1,51	1,38	1,24	1,36
O'zgarish 2024/2019	0,95	1,06	1,03	2,01	1,33	1,56	1,51	1,28

Manba: www.stat.uz, www.stat.gov.kz, <https://taldau.stat.gov.kz/ru/>
www.stat.gov.kg saytlari ma'lumotlari asosida muallif tomonidan tuzilgan. [4], [5], [6]

3-jadvalning birinchi uch ustunida sanoatda bandlar soni mamlakatlar kesimida aks ettirilgan bo'lib, O'zbekistonda bandlar sonining 2015–2024-yillarda deyarli barqaror saqlanib, ayrim yillarda qisqarishi sanoat o'sishining ekstensiv emasligini ko'rsatadi. Qozog'istonda bandlar sonining sekin, ammo izchil oshishi sanoat rivojlanishining nisbatan barqaror mehnat bazasiga tayanganini anglatadi. Qirg'izistonda esa bandlar sonining tezroq o'sishi sanoat ishlab chiqarishining ko'proq ekstensiv omillarga bog'liqligidan dalolat beradi. Keyingi uch ustunda keltirilgan bir bandga to'g'ri keladigan sanoat mahsuloti hajmi O'zbekistonda keskin oshib, mehnat unumdorligining sezilarli yaxshilanganini ko'rsatadi. Qozog'istonda ushbu ko'rsatkich yuqori bo'lsa-da, o'sish sur'atlarining tebranishi xomashyo sektoriga bog'liqlik bilan izohlanadi. Umuman olganda, 3-jadval sanoat rivojlanishining mamlakatlar kesimida intensivlik darajasi turlicha ekanini va O'zbekiston sanoati samaradorlik bosqichiga o'tayotganini ko'rsatadi. Jadvalning dastlabki uch ustuni mehnat unumdorligi o'sish sur'atlarining mamlakatlar kesimidagi farqlarini ko'rsatib, O'zbekistonda 2017-yildan keyin mazkur ko'rsatkichning sezilarli tezlashganini tasdiqlaydi. Bu holat sanoatni modernizatsiya qilish, texnologik yangilanish va kapital sig'imining ortishi bilan izohlanadi. 3-jadvalning 8-ustunida O'zbekistonda bir bandga to'g'ri keladigan sanoat mahsuloti hajmining Qozog'iston ko'rsatkichiga nisbati keltirilgan bo'lib, ushbu nisbat 2015–2024-yillarda 0,23–0,43 oralig'ida shakllangan. Bu natija Qozog'istonda mehnat unumdorligi yuqori ekanini ko'rsatsa-da, nisbatning vaqt o'tishi bilan oshib borishi O'zbekiston sanoatida samaradorlikning tezroq o'sayotganidan dalolat beradi. 9-ustunda esa O'zbekistonning bir bandga to'g'ri keladigan sanoat mahsuloti hajmi Qirg'iziston ko'rsatkichiga nisbatan ifodalangan bo'lib, ushbu nisbat 1,3–2,3 barobar atrofida shakllangan. Bu O'zbekiston sanoatining mehnat unumdorligi bo'yicha Qirg'izistondan ancha ustun ekanini ko'rsatadi. Shu bilan birga, nisbatning vaqt o'tishi bilan ortib borishi O'zbekistonda sanoat samaradorligining oshib borayotganini, Qirg'izistonda esa texnologik va kapital cheklovlar saqlanib qolayotganini anglatadi. Mazkur tadqiqotda 3-jadval sanoatda bandlar soniga to'g'ri keladigan sanoat mahsuloti hajmining kelgusi davr uchun prognoz ko'rsatkichlarini aniqlash maqsadida keltirilgan. Oldingi jadvallarda sanoat rivojlanishining joriy va o'tgan davrdagi holati tahlil qilingan bo'lsa, 3-jadval ushbu tendensiyalarning barqarorligi va davomiyligini baholash imkonini beradi. 3-jadvaldagi 5-6-7-ustunlar asosida prognoz qilish imkoniyati mavjud. Prognozlar MS Excel dasturida oddiy vaqtga bog'liq trend modellar orqali hisoblangan. Prognoz ko'rsatkichlari sanoat rivojlanishining intensiv omillarga tayangan holda shakllanayotganini aniqlashga xizmat qiladi. Shuningdek, jadval mamlakatlar kesimida sanoat samaradorligining kelgusidagi nisbiy holatini solishtirish imkonini beradi. Bu yondashuv sanoat siyosati uchun oldindan baholash va rejalashtirish nuqtayi nazaridan muhimdir.

4-jadval. Sanoatda bandlar soniga mos sanoat mahsuloti hajmi prognozi

Yillar	Sanoat mahsuloti hajmining prognozi (1000 dollar)			O'zbekiston sanoat mahsuloti hajmining nisbati	
	O'zbekistonda	Qozog'istonda	Qirg'izistonda	Qozog'istonga nisbatan	Qirg'izistonga nisbatan
2024	39,101	98,334	17,719	0,40	2,21
2025	46,730	106,060	20,056	0,44	2,33
2026	55,498	114,429	22,758	0,49	2,44
2027	65,409	123,440	25,824	0,53	2,53
2028	76,462	133,094	29,253	0,57	2,61
Farq (+/-) 2028–2024	37,361	34,760	11,534	0,18	0,41
O'zgarish 2028/2024	95,54	35,35	65,10	44,47	18,44

4-jadval natijalari O'zbekistonda sanoatda bandlar soniga to'g'ri keladigan sanoat

mahsuloti hajmi kelgusi yillarda tez sur'atlarda oshib borishini ko'rsatadi. Prognozlarga ko'ra, mazkur ko'rsatkichning o'sish sur'ati Qozog'iston va Qirg'izistonga nisbatan yuqoriroq bo'lib, bu O'zbekistonda sanoat samaradorligining oshib borayotganidan dalolat beradi.

Qozog'istonda prognoz ko'rsatkichlari yuqori mutlaq qiymatlarda shakllansada, o'sish sur'atlarining nisbatan pastligi sanoat rivojlanishining yetuk bosqichga kirganini anglatadi. Qirg'izistonda esa prognoz natijalari sanoat samaradorligi o'sishining sekinroq kechishini ko'rsatadi. Umuman olganda, 4-jadval O'zbekiston sanoatining o'rta muddatda raqobatbardoshligini kuchaytirish imkoniyatlari mavjudligini tasdiqlaydi.

Olib borilgan tadqiqot natijalari O'zbekiston, Qozog'iston va Qirg'iziston respublikalarida sanoat rivojlanishining miqyosi, sur'atlari va samaradorligi bo'yicha sezilarli farqlar mavjudligini ko'rsatdi. Tahlillar O'zbekistonda sanoat mahsuloti hajmi va mehnat unumdorligining so'nggi yillarda barqaror o'sib borayotganini tasdiqlaydi. Valyuta liberallasuvi, investitsiya muhitining yaxshilanishi va sanoatni diversifikatsiya qilishga qaratilgan siyosat sanoat rivojlanishiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatgan. Qozog'istonda sanoat rivoji yuqori mutlaq ko'rsatkichlar bilan tavsiflansada, uning xomashyo sektoriga bog'liqligi barqarorlikka ma'lum darajada salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. Qirg'izistonda esa sanoat rivojlanishi cheklangan ishlab chiqarish bazasi va kapital yetishmasligi bilan izohlanadi.

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